

A Hybrid Approach of Neutrosophic with MULTIMOORA in Application of Personnel Selection

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Abstract: Personnel selection is an important key for the success of human resource management in organizations. The main challenge faces organization is to determine the most proper candidates. To match organization requirements, the decision-makers do their best to achieve the most appropriate solutions. The process of choosing between candidates is a very complex and confused task. The environment of decision making is a multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) of various and conflicting criteria and alternatives in addition to the environmental conditions of uncertainty and incomplete information. Hence, this paper contributes to support the personnel selection process with non-classical methods by the integration of neutrosophic theory with MULTIMOORA. A case study is applied on Telecommunication Company in smart village Cairo Egypt. The case study applies the hybrid approach to attain to most appropriate solutions in the problem of personnel selection.

Keywords: Personnel selection, Multi-criteria decision making (MCDM), Neutrosophic Sets, MULTIMOORA.

1. Introduction

The competitiveness of organizations can be achieved by the ability of efficient employment [1]. For organization, the most effective part of Human Resource Management is the personnel selection process [2]. The classical methods are used in organizations to select candidates were not sufficient enough and need to be enhanced, to continue proceeding with globalization and rivalry [3]. The numerous and conflict personal criteria make the decision maker confused [4]. The fuzzy set theory appears as an important tool to provide a decision framework that incorporates imprecise judgments inherent in the personnel selection process [5, 6] The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) is used to format the complex problems into a hierarchical form of criterions, alternatives, and goals to support decision makers in the selection process [7]. Classical AHP method has been stretched to numerous fuzzy versions, because of partial information and ambiguity. Although the theories of fuzzy have been developed and generalized but cannot deal with all kinds of uncertainties in real problems. Indeed, sure kinds of uncertainties, such as indeterminate and inconsistent information,

cannot be managed. Therefore, some new theories are required to present the truth membership, indeterminacy membership and falsity membership simultaneously this called neutrosophic sets. Unlike fuzzy, the neutrosophic sets deal with uncertain, inconsistent, and incomplete information in many researches [32-40]. The personnel selection is a multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) problem that contains multiple criteria, alternatives, and decision makers to obtain the best candidate to be hire in organization [8]. The use of neutrosophic in personnel selection aids decision makers in the case of uncertainty and inconsistent information to achieve organizations objectives [9]. Sometimes neither of candidates satisfies the vision and objectives of organizations. Therefore, in this study we extend the neutrosophic personnel selection with MULTIMOORA method to encompass the measurement value the method reference level.

The Multi-Objective Optimization by Ratio Analysis (MOORA) method has been introduced by [10]. The MOORA is composed of ratio system, reference point [11-13]. The method MOORA enhanced to MULTIMOORA by adding full Multiplicative Form and employing Dominance Theory to obtain a final rank [2]. The ordinary MULTIMOORA method has been proposed for usage with crisp numbers. MULTIMOORA can solve larger numbers of complex decision-making problems by adding several extensions to solve wide range of problems. The hybrid approach handles the current obstacles and challenges by recommending the most appropriate candidates in the environment of uncertainty and incomplete information.

The structure of this paper ordered as follows: section 2 illustrates some related studies of personnel selection. Section 3 represents the hybrid methodology of neutrosophic with MULTIMOORA method to aid decision makers to choose most appropriate candidate to achieve the goal of organization. Section 4 represents an empirical case study for the proposed hybrid approach. Section 5 summarizes the research key points and the future trends.

2. Related Studies

The processes of personnel selection in organizations can be affected by many conditions e.g. change the nature of work, governmental regulations, client's behavior, development of new technology, and others [14-16]. The traditional methods are not appropriate enough to keep on globalization. Hence organizations needs to make enhancement on personnel selection problem especially in the field of the judgments of decision makers by integrating advanced tools to decision support system [17,18]. In [19-22] describe the method of AHP with a fuzzy multi-criteria decision making algorithms for solving the personnel selection problems. In [23-25] describe the fuzzy MCDM with TOPSIS method to solve personnel selection problem using linguistic and numerical scales with different data sources to permit decision makers to evaluate candidate's information. In [19] illustrate the AHP method combined with fuzzy to solve personnel selection problem for information systems.

The MULTIMOORA method is extended by researchers to handle several MCDM problems [26, 27]. In [2,] the use of MULTIMOORA with a fuzzy MCDM were not the most appropriate methodology. Due to the situations of uncertainty and incomplete information, researches recommend to integrate neutrosophic sets in personnel selection problem [28, 29]. We propose to be the first to applying the neutrosophic sets with MULTIMOORA method to aid decision makers to achieve to the most appropriate candidates.

3. Methodology

A hybrid MULTIMOORA method with neutrosophic is applied in personnel selection problem to select the best candidate to hire in organization. The MULTIMOORA method is used to solve personnel selection problem. In Fig. 1 represents conceptual flow of personnel selection to obtain ideal solution. In Fig. 2 represents the structure of methodology phase to apply MULTIMOORA method with neutrosophic. The phases for the hybrid approach are mentioned as follows:

Figure 1. conceptual flow of personnel selection problem.

Phase1: Acquire expert information in neutrosophic environment.

- Determine the study goal, criteria, and alternative.
- Use neutrosophic scale mentioned in Table 1 [30].
- Create pairwise matrix of decision making judgments using the following form:

$$C^M = \begin{bmatrix} B_{11}^M & \dots & B_{1z}^M \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ B_{y1}^M & \dots & B_{yz}^M \end{bmatrix} \tag{1}$$

- Aggregate pairwise matrix by:

$$B_{uv} = \frac{\sum_{M=1}^M \langle (l_{uv}^M, m_{uv}^M, u_{uv}^M); T_{uv}^M, I_{uv}^M, F_{uv}^M \rangle}{M} \tag{2}$$

Where, M represents number of decision makers, $l_{uv}^M, m_{uv}^M, u_{uv}^M$ are lower, middle and upper bound of neutrosophic number, $T_{uv}^M, I_{uv}^M, F_{uv}^M$ are truth, indeterminacy and falsity.

- Construct the initial pairwise comparison matrix as mentioned:

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} B_{11} & \dots & B_{1z} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ B_{y1} & \dots & B_{yz} \end{bmatrix} \tag{3}$$

- Convert neutrosophic scales to crisp values by using score function of B_{uv} [31]:

$$s(B_{uv}) = \left| (l_{uv} * m_{uv} * u_{uv})^{\frac{T_{uv}+I_{uv}+F_{uv}}{9}} \right| \tag{4}$$

where l, m, u represents lower, middle and upper of the scale neutrosophic numbers.

Phase2: Calculate weights of criteria.

- Compute the average of row

$$w_u = \frac{\sum_{v=1}^z (B_{uv})}{z}; u = 1,2,3, \dots \dots y; v = 1,2,3, \dots \dots z; \tag{5}$$

- The normalization of crisp value is calculated using the following equation

$$w_u^y = \frac{w_u}{\sum_{u=1}^y w_u}; u = 1,2,3, \dots \dots y \tag{6}$$

Phase3: Evaluate expert judgement using consistency rate

Check the consistency of matrix using table 2 and for detailed information in [31]

- Compute weighted columns by multiplying the weight of priority by each value in the pairwise comparison matrix [31].
- The weighted sum values are divided with the corresponding priority.
- Compute the mean of the previous step denoted as λ_{max} .
- Compute consistency index $CI = \frac{\lambda_{max}-n}{n-1}$, where n the number of criteria.
- Calculate consistency ratio by the use for the mentioned equation

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI} \tag{7}$$

Where, CR is the consistency rate, CI is consistency Index. RI is the random index for consistency matrix as mentioned in Table 3.

Phase4: MULTIMOORA Method

The decision judgments between criteria and alternatives will be collected and obtained by the use of form (1). Then, apply Equation (2) to make a general vision of aggregation of experts. Finally, apply Equation (4) to change neutrosophic scale values to crisp values. The MULTIMOORA method consists of: ratio system, reference point and full multiplicative form.

Phase4.1: Ratio System

- The first step of ratio system is to calculate the normalize of the decision matrix as mentioned:

$$B_{uv}^* = \frac{B_{uv}}{\sqrt[2]{\sum_{u=1}^y B_{uv}^2}}; u = 1,2,3, \dots \dots, y \text{ and } v = 1,2,3 \dots \dots, z. \tag{8}$$

- Compute the beneficial criteria (Y^+) is the summation of beneficial criteria of weight normalized elements of matrix. Then non-beneficial criteria denoted as (Y^-). Finally subtract sum of beneficial criteria from sum of non-beneficial criteria. (NB. In this study all criterions are beneficial)

$$Y^+ = \sum_{v=1}^g w_v B_{uv}^* \tag{9}$$

$$Y^- = \sum_{v=1}^z w_v B_{uv}^* \tag{10}$$

- The next formula represents number of criteria to be maximized and (z-g) represents number of criteria to be minimized.

$$Y^* = \sum_{v=1}^g w_v B_{uv}^* - \sum_{v=g+1}^z w_v B_{uv}^* \tag{11}$$

,where w_v is the weight of criteria

- Finally, Rank the alternatives

Phase4.2: Reference point

The second step of neutrosophic MULTIMOORA is reference point

- Compute reference point to be maximized

$$r_v = \max_u(w_v(B_z^*)_{uv}). \tag{12}$$

- Compute reference point to be minimized

$$r_v = \min_u(w_v(B_z^*)_{uv}). \tag{13}$$

- Compute deviation of reference point

$$\min_v \left(\max_u |(r_u - w_v(x_z^*)_{uv})| \right). \tag{14}$$

Phase4.3: Full multiplicative form

The third step of neutrosophic MULTIMOORA is full multiplicative form

- Compute utility of the alternative

$$U_u = \frac{E_u}{F_u} \tag{15}$$

$$E_u = \prod_{v=1}^g w_v(B_z^*)_{uv} \tag{16}$$

$$F_u = \prod_{v=g+1}^g w_v(B_z^*)_{uv} \tag{17}$$

The first component E_u represents the product of criteria of u th alternative to be maximized. The second component F_u represents the product criteria of u th alternative to be minimized.

- Finally apply the dominance theory to obtain final rank

Table1. Neutrosophic triangular scale (linguistic terms)

Saaty scale	Caption	Neutrosophic triangular scale
1	Evenly significant	$\tilde{1} = \langle \langle 1, 1 \rangle; 0.50, 0.50, 0.50 \rangle$
3	A little significant	$\tilde{3} = \langle \langle 2, 3, 4 \rangle; 0.30, 0.75, 0.70 \rangle$
5	Powerfully significant	$\tilde{5} = \langle \langle 4, 5, 6 \rangle; 0.80, 0.15, 0.20 \rangle$
7	Completely Powerfully significant	$\tilde{7} = \langle \langle 6, 7, 8 \rangle; 0.90, 0.10, 0.10 \rangle$
9	Absolutely significant	$\tilde{9} = \langle \langle 9, 9, 0 \rangle; 1.00, 0.00, 0.00 \rangle$
2	Sporadic values between two close scales	$\tilde{2} = \langle \langle 1, 2, 3 \rangle; 0.40, 0.60, 0.65 \rangle$
4		$\tilde{4} = \langle \langle 3, 4, 5 \rangle; 0.35, 0.60, 0.40 \rangle$
6		$\tilde{6} = \langle \langle 5, 6, 7 \rangle; 0.70, 0.25, 0.30 \rangle$
8		$\tilde{8} = \langle \langle 7, 8, 9 \rangle; 0.85, 0.10, 0.15 \rangle$

Table 2. The consistency rate for pair-wise comparison matrix

N	4 × 4	5 × 5	N > 4
CR ≤	0.58	0.90	1.12

Table 3. Random Consistency index for various criterions

Size of matrix	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Random Consistency	0.00	0.00	0.58	0.90	1.12	1.24	1.32	1.41	1.45	1.49

Figure 2. Personnel selection and MULTIMOORA method

4. An Empirical Case Study

In this section, the case study is about personnel selection in a telecommunication company in smart village in Egypt. The case study applies the hybrid methodology of neutrosophic with MULTIMOORA method. In order to make a general image for the telecommunication company, we

adopt eight criteria, seven alternatives, and four decision makers. Figure 3 shows the relations between criteria and alternatives. The telecommunication goal is to hire best candidate to achieve competitive organization goals.

Figure 3. The AHP Structure for criteria and alternatives

Phase 1: Represent expert judgments in neutrosophic environment

- Create neutrosophic triangular scale (linguistic term) in Table 1.
- Create the general vision pairwise comparison matrix of criteria in Table 4 in form (1).
- Aggregate pairwise comparison matrix of criteria using Equations (2) and form in (3).
- Convert aggregate pairwise comparison matrix of criteria to crisp value in Table 5 using Equation (4).

Table 4. The pairwise comparison matrix of criteria of decision maker judgments

		C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
	C1	$\langle \langle 1, 1, 1 \rangle; 0.50, 0.50 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 4, 5, 6 \rangle; 0.80, 0.15, 0.20 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 1, 1, 1 \rangle; 0.50, 0.50 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 1, 1, 1 \rangle; 0.50, 0.50 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 4, 5, 6 \rangle; 0.80, 0.15, 0.20 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 3, 4, 5 \rangle; 0.35, 0.60, 0.40 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 7, 8, 9 \rangle; 0.85, 0.10, 0.15 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 7, 8, 9 \rangle; 0.85, 0.10, 0.15 \rangle$
	C2	$\langle \langle 4, 5, 6 \rangle; 0.80, 0.15, 0.20 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 1, 1, 1 \rangle; 0.50, 0.50 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 1, 1, 1 \rangle; 0.50, 0.50 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 4, 5, 6 \rangle; 0.80, 0.15, 0.20 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 7, 8, 9 \rangle; 0.85, 0.10, 0.15 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 4, 5, 6 \rangle; 0.80, 0.15, 0.20 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 1, 1, 1 \rangle; 0.50, 0.50 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 1, 1, 1 \rangle; 0.50, 0.50 \rangle$
	C3	$\langle \langle 1, 1, 1 \rangle; 0.50, 0.50 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 1, 1, 1 \rangle; 0.50, 0.50 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 1, 1, 1 \rangle; 0.50, 0.50 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 5, 6, 7 \rangle; 0.70, 0.70, 0.70 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 4, 5, 6 \rangle; 0.80, 0.15, 0.20 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 1, 2, 3 \rangle; 0.40, 0.60, 0.40 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 4, 5, 6 \rangle; 0.80, 0.15, 0.20 \rangle$	$\langle \langle 7, 8, 9 \rangle; 0.85, 0.10, 0.15 \rangle$

DM1			0.50, 0.50>	0.50, 0.50>	0.25, 0.30>	0.15, 0.20>	0.60, 0.65>	0.15, 0.20>	0.10, 0.15>
	C4	1/< <1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	1/< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	1/< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>
	C5	1/< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	1/< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	1/< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	1/< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>
	C6	1/< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	1/< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	1/< <1 ,2, 3>;0.40, 0.60, 0.65>	1/< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	1/< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>
	C7	1/< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	1/< <1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	1/< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	1/< <1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	1/< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	1/< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>
	C8	1/< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	1/< <1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	1/< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	1/< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	1/< <1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	1/< <1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	1/< <1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>
DM2	C1	< <1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>
	C2	1/< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>
	C3	1/< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	1/< <1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>
	C4	1/< <1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	1/< <1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	1/< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>

	C5	1/< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	1/< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	1/< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	1/< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>
	C6	1/< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	1/< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	1/< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	1/< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	1/< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>
	C7	1/< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	1/< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	1/< <1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	1/< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	1/< <1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	1/< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>
	C8	1/< <1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	1/< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	1/< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	1/< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	1/< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	1/< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	1/< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>
DM3	C1	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>
	C2	1/< <1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>
	C3	1/< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	1/< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>
	C4	1/< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	1/< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	1/< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>
	C5	1/< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	1/< <1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	1/< <1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	1/< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>
	C6	1/< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	1/< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	1/< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	1/< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	1/< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>

	C7	1/< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	1/<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	1/<<5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	1/<<4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	1/<<3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	1/<<3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>
	C8	1/< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	1/<<5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	1/<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	1/<<7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	1/<<5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	1/<<3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	1/<<5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>
DM4	C1	< <1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>
	C2	1/< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>
	C3	1/< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	1/<<7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>
	C4	1/< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	1/<<5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	1/<<5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>
	C5	1/< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	1/<<5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	1/<<3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	1/<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>
	C6	1/< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	1/<<4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	1/<<5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	1/<<4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	1/<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>
	C7	1/< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	1/<<3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	1/<<5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	1/<<3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	1/<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	1/<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>
	C8	1/<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	1/<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	1/<<3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	1/<<3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	1/<<7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	1/<<5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	1/<<4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	<<1, 1, 1 >;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>

Table 5. Crisp value of aggregated pairwise comparison matrix of criteria.

Criteria	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
C1	1	1.88288	1.88288	1.85098	2.01946	2.04291	2.03948	1.76092
C2	0.53110	1	1.77829	1.82446	1.94923	1.93354	1.53537	1.66246
C3	0.53110	0.56233	1	2.05393	1.79510	2.02662	1.89927	1.95726
C4	0.54025	0.54810	0.48687	1	2.01743	1.85375	1.82446	1.97178
C5	0.48949	0.51302	0.55707	0.49568	1	1.88588	1.58172	2.01743
C6	0.48949	0.51718	0.49343	0.53944	0.53025	1	1.71033	1.81143
C7	0.49032	0.65130	0.52651	0.54810	0.63222	0.58468	1	1.89927
C8	0.56788	0.60151	0.51091	0.50715	0.45991	0.55205	0.52651	1

Phase 2: Calculate weight of criteria as mentioned in Fig. (4).

- Compute the average of row.

$$w_1 = 14.47951 \quad w_2 = 12.21445 \quad w_3 = 11.82561 \quad w_4 = 10.24264 \quad w_5 = 8.54029 \quad w_6 = 7.09155 \quad w_7 = 6.3324 \quad w_8 = 4.72592$$

- The normalization of crisp value is calculated.

$$w_1 = 0.1919026 \quad w_2 = 0.1618829 \quad w_3 = 0.1567294 \quad w_4 = 0.1357497 \quad w_5 = 0.1131878 \quad w_6 = 0.0939871 \quad w_7 = 0.0839257 \quad w_8 = 0.0626344$$

$$\sum w_i = 1.$$

Figure 4. Pie chart weights of criteria

Phase 3: Check consistency rate

- Compute weighted sum

$$w_1 = 1.74501 \ w_2 = 1.4254 \ w_3 = 1.30403 \ w_4 = 1.08356 \ w_5 = 0.88104 \ w_6 = 0.73916 \ w_7 = 0.68578 \ w_8 = 0.56598$$

- Divide weighted sum by weight of criteria

$$w_1 = 9.09320 \ w_2 = 8.80513 \ w_3 = 8.32026 \ w_4 = 7.98204 \ w_5 = 7.78387 \ w_6 = 7.86448 \ w_7 = 8.17127 \ w_8 = 9.03624$$

- Divide summation of Weighted sum by the number of criteria 8
- Compute $\lambda_{max} = 8.38206$

- Compute $CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1} = \frac{8.38206 - 8}{8 - 1} = 0.05458$

- Compute $CR = \frac{CI}{RI} = \frac{0.05458}{1.41} = 0.03870$.

Hence, the pair-wise comparison matrix is consistent and follow the next phase of MULTIMOORA Method

Phase 4: MULTIMOORA Method Calculations

- A session is performed with four decision makers and the collected judgments presented in table 6.
- Aggregate judgments of decision matrix of four decision makers using Equation (2).
- Compute crisp value of aggregated decision matrix using Equation (4) and mentioned in Table 7.

Table 6. The judgments for multiple decision makers

	Criteria/ Alternatives	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	
DM1	A1	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <1 ,2, 3>;0.40, 0.60, 0.65>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	
	A2	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	
	A3	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	
	A4	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <1 ,2, 3>;0.40, 0.60, 0.65>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <1 ,2, 3>;0.40, 0.60, 0.65>	< <1 ,2, 3>;0.40, 0.60, 0.65>	< <1 ,2, 3>;0.40, 0.60, 0.65>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>
	A5	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 1>;0.50,	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50,	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50,	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80,	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80,	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85,	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85,	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85,	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80,

		0.10, 0.15>	0.50, 0.50>	0.50, 0.50>	0.15, 0.20>	0.15, 0.20>	0.10, 0.15>	0.10, 0.15>	0.15, 0.20>
	A6	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>
	A7	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>
DM2	A1	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>
	A2	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>
	A3	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>
	A4	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <1 ,2, 3>;0.40, 0.60, 0.65>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <1 ,2, 3>;0.40, 0.60, 0.65>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>
	A5	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>
	A6	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>
	A7	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>

DM3	A1	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>
	A2	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>
	A3	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <1 ,2, 3>;0.40, 0.60, 0.65>
	A4	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <1 ,2, 3>;0.40, 0.60, 0.65>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>
	A5	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>
	A6	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>
	A7	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>
DM4	A1	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>
	A2	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>
	A3	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <5 ,6, 7>;0.70, 0.25, 0.30>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>

A4	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50>	< <1 ,2, 3>;0.40, 0.60, 0.65>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <1 ,2, 3>;0.40, 0.60, 0.65>	< <1 ,2, 3>;0.40, 0.60, 0.65>
A5	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <3 ,4, 5>;0.35, 0.60, 0.40>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>
A6	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>
A7	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <1 ,1, 1>;0.50, 0.50, 0.50>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <7 ,8 ,9>;0.85, 0.10, 0.15>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>	< <4 ,5, 6>;0.80, 0.15, 0.20>

Table 7. The aggregated pairwise matrix for multiple decision maker's judgments

Criteria/ Alternatives	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
A1	1.88288	1.96309	2.01160	1.93540	1.88606	1.99504	1.99504	2.03414
A2	1.38248	2.00514	1.97958	2.073329	1.98669	2.25679	2.073329	2.12321
A3	1.88288	2.06542	1.985350	1.95726	1.99504	2.03414	1.382488	2.063838
A4	1.98669	1.96418	1.77208	1.55075	1.99504	1.73960	1.21198	1.11336
A5	1.77829	1.75314	1.382488	1.77829	1.617809	1.915488	2.042910	1.88288
A6	1.61780	1.98669	1.88288	1.38248	1.38248	1.93354	1.986697	1.996661
A7	1.88288	1.88288	1.93354	1	1.762838	1.93354	1.97178	1.617809

Phase 4.1: The ratio system

- Calculate normalization of decision matrix in using Equation (8), and mentioned in Table 8.
- Calculate Y^+ (weight normalized) using Equation (9) in Table 9.
- $Y^- = 0$ because all criteria are beneficial.
- The ranks of ratio system ranking are mentioned in Table 10.

Table 8. The normalization matrix

Criteria/ Alternatives	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
A1	0.39896	0.38088	0.40856	0.42899	0.39241	0.38124	0.41009	0.41269
A2	0.29293	0.38904	0.40205	0.45956	0.41335	0.43126	0.42618	0.43076
A3	0.39896	0.40074	0.40322	0.43383	0.41508	0.38872	0.24817	0.41872
A4	0.42095	0.38109	0.35991	0.34373	0.41508	0.33243	0.24912	0.22588
A5	0.37680	0.34015	0.28078	0.39416	0.33659	0.36604	0.41993	0.38200
A6	0.34279	0.38546	0.38241	0.30643	0.28763	0.36949	0.40837	0.40509
A7	0.39896	0.36532	0.39270	0.22165	0.36677	0.36949	0.40530	0.32822

Table 9. The Y⁺ (Weighted normalized)

Criteria/ Alternatives	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
A1	0.076561	0.061657	0.064033	0.058235	0.044416	0.035831	0.034417	0.025848
A2	0.056214	0.062978	0.063013	0.062385	0.046786	0.040532	0.035767	0.026980
A3	0.076561	0.064872	0.063196	0.058892	0.046981	0.036534	0.020827	0.026226
A4	0.080781	0.061691	0.056408	0.046661	0.046981	0.031244	0.020907	0.014147
A5	0.072308	0.055064	0.044006	0.053507	0.038097	0.034403	0.035242	0.023926
A6	0.065782	0.062399	0.059934	0.041597	0.032556	0.034727	0.034272	0.025372
A7	0.076561	0.059139	0.061547	0.030088	0.041513	0.034727	0.034015	0.020557
	461	061	635	921	889	294	086	863

Table 10. The ranks of Ratio system

Alternatives	Y [*]	Ranking
A1	0.401001	1
A2	0.394658	2
A3	0.394094	3
A4	0.358825	4
A5	0.356557	7
A6	0.356643	6
A7	0.358151	5

Phase 4.2: The reference point

- Calculate Reference point r_r using Eq. (12) in table 11
- Calculate deviations from reference point using Eq. (14) in table 12
- The Reference point ranking mentioned in table 13.

Table 11. Reference point

Criteria	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
R _j	0.080781 399	0.064872 953	0.064033 364	0.062385 132	0.046981 992	0.040532 877	0.035767 455	0.026980 394

Table 13. Deviations from reference point.

Criteria/Alternative	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
A1	0.00421 9938	0.00321 4994	0.00000 000	0.00414 9868	0.00256 5967	0.00470 1235	0.00135 0365	0.00113 1803
A2	0.02456 737	0.00189 403	0.00102 0309	0.00000 000	0.00019 5815	0.00000 000	0.00000 000	0.00000 000
A3	0.00421 9938	0.00000 000	0.00083 6935	0.00349 284	0.00000 000	0.00399 8211	0.01493 9614	0.00075 4118
A4	0.00000 000	0.00318 0999	0.00762 4886	0.01572 3888	0.00000 000	0.00928 8745	0.01485 9885	0.01283 2536
A5	0.00847 2499	0.00980 8485	0.02002 6883	0.00887 803	0.00888 411	0.00612 9839	0.00052 4536	0.00305 4053
A6	0.01499 9107	0.00247 357	0.00409 8474	0.02078 7351	0.01442 5785	0.00580 5583	0.00149 4717	0.00160 7825
A7	0.00421 9938	0.00573 3892	0.00248 5729	0.03229 6211	0.00546 8103	0.00580 5583	0.00175 2369	0.00642 2531

Table13. Rank reference point

Alternative	Max value (Deviations from reference point)	Rank reference point
A1	0.004701235	7
A2	0.02456737	2
A3	0.014939614	6
A4	0.015723888	5
A5	0.020026883	4
A6	0.020787351	3
A7	0.032296211	1

Phase 4.3: Full multiplicative form

- Compute utility of the alternative using Equation (15), (16) and (17) in Table 14.
- The full Multiplicative form ranking in Table 15.

According to Table 16 and Fig. 5, the final rank recommends alternative one as the best alternative, while alternative four as the worst alternative.

Table 14. Utility and Rank of full multiplicative form.

Alternatives	Utility (U_u)	Rank Multiplicative form
A1	2.49235E-11	2
A2	2.54691E-11	1
A3	1.73317E-11	3
A4	5.69554E-12	7
A5	1.03618E-11	4
A6	1.00614E-11	5
A7	8.45311E-12	6

Table15. The final rank according to the proposed hybrid methodology

Alternatives	Ratio system	Reference point	Full multiplicative	(Final Rank)
A1	1	7	2	1
A2	2	2	1	2
A3	3	6	3	3
A4	4	5	7	7
A5	7	4	4	4
A6	6	3	5	6
A7	5	1	6	5

Figure 5. The final rank recommendation

5. Conclusions

Personnel selection is an important issue that effect on the competitive advantages for organizations. Decision makers take decisions for complex problems with various criterions and

alternatives with surrounded environment of uncertain and incomplete information. The traditional methods cannot achieve to the proper solutions. In addition fuzzy cannot handle the conditions of uncertainty and inconsistency. The study proposes to use neutrosophic sets to handle the environmental conditions of uncertainty and inconsistent information, in addition extend study with MULTIMOORA method to choose the most appropriate candidate. A case study is applied on smart village Cairo, Egypt, on Telecommunication Company shows the effectiveness for the proposed method and provides final decision to hire the most appropriate candidate for attaining success of enterprises. The future work includes evolutionary algorithms for selecting the most effective criterions. In addition, applies other methodologies e.g. DENTAL to improve the selection process.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Liang, R.-x., Z.-b. Jiang, and J.-q. Wang, A linguistic Neutrosophic Multi-Criteria Group Decision-Making Method to University Human Resource Management. *Symmetry*, 2018. 10(9).
2. Baležentis, A., T. Baležentis, and W.K.M. Brauers, Personnel selection based on computing with words and fuzzy MULTIMOORA. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 2012. 39(9): p. 7961-7967.
3. Nabeeh, N.A., et al., An Integrated Neutrosophic-TOPSIS Approach and Its Application to Personnel Selection: A New Trend in Brain Processing and Analysis. *IEEE Access*, 2019. 7: p. 29734-29744.
4. Şahin, R. and M. Yiğider, A Multi-criteria neutrosophic group decision making method based TOPSIS for supplier selection. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1412.5077*, 2014.
5. Karsak, E.E., Personnel selection using a fuzzy MCDM approach based on ideal and anti-ideal solutions, in *Multiple criteria decision making in the new millennium*. 2001, Springer. p. 393-402.
6. Liang, G.-S. and M.-J.J. Wang, Personnel selection using fuzzy MCDM algorithm. *European journal of operational research*, 1994. 78(1): p. 22-33.
7. Saaty, T.L., A scaling method for priorities in hierarchical structures. *Journal of mathematical psychology*, 1977. 15(3): p. 234-281.
8. Tian, Z.-p., et al., Multi-criteria decision-making method based on a cross-entropy with interval neutrosophic sets. *International Journal of Systems Science*, 2016. 47(15): p. 3598-3608.
9. Smarandache, F., A unifying field in Logics: Neutrosophic Logic, in *Philosophy*. 1999, American Research Press. p. 1-141.
10. Brauers, W.K. and E.K. Zavadskas, The MOORA method and its application to privatization in a transition economy. *Control and Cybernetics*, 2006. 35: p. 445-469.
11. Balezentiene, L., D. Streimikiene, and T. Balezentis, Fuzzy decision support methodology for sustainable energy crop selection. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 2013. 17: p. 83-93.
12. Kumar, R. and A. Ray. Selection of material under conflicting situation using simple ratio optimization technique. in *Proceedings of Fourth International Conference on Soft Computing for Problem Solving*. 2015. Springer.
13. Aytaç Adalı, E. and A. Tuş Işık, The multi-objective decision making methods based on MULTIMOORA and MOOSRA for the laptop selection problem. *Journal of Industrial Engineering International*, 2016. 13(2): p. 229-237.

14. Hough, L.M. and F.L. Oswald, Personnel selection: Looking toward the future--Remembering the past. *Annual review of psychology*, 2000. 51(1): p. 631-664.
15. Liao, S.-h., Knowledge management technologies and applications—literature review from 1995 to 2002. *Expert systems with applications*, 2003. 25(2): p. 155-164.
16. Beckers, A.M. and M.Z. Bsat, A DSS classification model for research in human resource information systems. *Information Systems Management*, 2002. 19(3): p. 41-50.
17. Shih, H.-S., L.-C. Huang, and H.-J. Shyur, Recruitment and selection processes through an effective GDSS. *Computers & Mathematics with Applications*, 2005. 50(10-12): p. 1543-1558.
18. Chien, C.-F. and L.-F. Chen, Data mining to improve personnel selection and enhance human capital: A case study in high-technology industry. *Expert Systems with applications*, 2008. 34(1): p. 280-290.
19. Güngör, Z., G. Serhadlıoğlu, and S.E. Kesen, A fuzzy AHP approach to personnel selection problem. *Applied Soft Computing*, 2009. 9(2): p. 641-646.
20. Kahraman, C., et al., Fuzzy multi-criteria evaluation of industrial robotic systems. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 2007. 52(4): p. 414-433.
21. Hsu, T.-K., Y.-F. Tsai, and H.-H. Wu, The preference analysis for tourist choice of destination: A case study of Taiwan. *Tourism management*, 2009. 30(2): p. 288-297.
22. Benitez, J.M., J.C. Martín, and C. Román, Using fuzzy number for measuring quality of service in the hotel industry. *Tourism management*, 2007. 28(2): p. 544-555.
23. Dursun, M. and E.E. Karsak, A fuzzy MCDM approach for personnel selection. *Expert Systems with applications*, 2010. 37(6): p. 4324-4330.
24. Samanlioglu, F., et al., A fuzzy AHP–TOPSIS-based group decision-making approach to IT personnel selection. *International Journal of Fuzzy Systems*, 2018. 20(5): p. 1576-1591.
25. Shyjith, K., M. Ilankumaran, and S. Kumanan, Multi-criteria decision-making approach to evaluate optimum maintenance strategy in textile industry. *Journal of Quality in Maintenance Engineering*, 2008. 14(4): p. 375-386.
26. Zavadskas, E.K., et al., The interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy MULTIMOORA method for group decision making in engineering. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2015. 2015.
27. Stanujkic, D., et al., A neutrosophic extension of the MULTIMOORA method. *Informatika*, 2017. 28(1): p. 181-192.
28. Abdel-Basset, M., Manogaran, G., Gamal, A., & Smarandache, F. (2019). A group decision making framework based on neutrosophic TOPSIS approach for smart medical device selection. *Journal of medical systems*, 43(2), 38.
29. Muralidharan, C., N. Anantharaman, and S. Deshmukh, A multi-criteria group decisionmaking model for supplier rating. *Journal of supply chain management*, 2002. 38(3): p. 22-33.
30. M. Abdel-Basset, N. A. Nabeeh, H. A. El-Ghareeb, A. Aboelfetouh. Utilizing Neutrosophic Theory to Solve Transition Difficulties of IoT-Based Enterprises. *Enterprise Information Systems*, 2019
31. N. A. Nabeeh, M. Abdel-Basset, H. A. El-Ghareeb, A. Aboelfetouh. (2019). Neutrosophic Multi-Criteria Decision Making Approach for IoT-Based Enterprises. *IEEE Access*, 2019
32. Abdel-Basset, M., El-hoseny, M., Gamal, A., & Smarandache, F. (2019). A novel model for evaluation Hospital medical care systems based on plithogenic sets. *Artificial intelligence in medicine*, 100, 101710.
33. Abdel-Basset, M., Manogaran, G., Gamal, A., & Chang, V. (2019). A Novel Intelligent Medical Decision Support Model Based on Soft Computing and IoT. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*.
34. Abdel-Basset, M., Mohamed, R., Zaied, A. E. N. H., & Smarandache, F. (2019). A hybrid plithogenic decision-making approach with quality function deployment for selecting supply chain sustainability metrics. *Symmetry*, 11(7), 903.
35. Abdel-Baset, M., Chang, V., & Gamal, A. (2019). Evaluation of the green supply chain management practices: A novel neutrosophic approach. *Computers in Industry*, 108, 210-220.
36. Abdel-Basset, M., Saleh, M., Gamal, A., & Smarandache, F. (2019). An approach of TOPSIS technique for developing supplier selection with group decision making under type-2 neutrosophic number. *Applied Soft Computing*, 77, 438-452.
37. Abdel-Basset, M., Atef, A., & Smarandache, F. (2019). A hybrid Neutrosophic multiple criteria group decision making approach for project selection. *Cognitive Systems Research*, 57, 216-227.

38. Abdel-Basset, M., Smarandache, F., & Ye, J. (2018). Special issue on "Applications of neutrosophic theory in decision making-recent advances and future trends".
39. Son, N. T. K., Dong, N. P., Abdel-Basset, M., Manogaran, G., & Long, H. V. On the Stabilizability for a Class of Linear Time-Invariant Systems Under Uncertainty. *Circuits, Systems, and Signal Processing*, 1-42.
40. Chang, V., Abdel-Basset, M., & Ramachandran, M. (2019). Towards a reuse strategic decision pattern framework—from theories to practices. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 21(1), 27-44.

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